

VARIED INTENSITIES OF BENCH STEP TRAINING ON BREATH HOLDING TIME OF COLLEGE MEN STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of bench stepping exercise on selected physiological variable such as breath holding time. To achieve this purpose of the study, thirty male students studying in the Jawahar College of Arts and Sciences, Neyveli, were randomly selected as subjects and they were divided into three equal groups, each group consisted often subjects. Group I underwent bench stepping exercise for two days per week for eight weeks, Group II underwent bench stepping exercise for three days per week for eight weeks and Group III acted as control group who did not participate in any special training apart from their regular curricular activities. The subjects were tested on selected criterion variable breath holding rate at prior to and immediately after the training period. The selected criterion variables such as speed was measured by breath holding time was measured by holding the breath for maximum time respectively. The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the significant difference if any, between the experimental groups and control group on selected criterion variables separately. In all the cases, .05 level of confidence was fixed to test the significance, which was considered as an appropriate. It was concluded that the training groups, i.e. two days per week and three days per week training, has better improvement in breath holding time.

Key Words: Breath Holding Time & Bench Step Training

Introduction:

In general, the term exercise is used to improve Mari's physical, physiological and intellectual performance. In the field of physical educations and sports we speak exercise in the sense of preparing the sports persons for highest levels of performance. Briefly exercise is the physical, physiological and normal preparation of a athlete by means of physical exercises that is by applying varied intensity of work load.

Ultimate aim of exercise is achieving the highest possible individual performance in a given event or discipline. Specialized in one event or any other discipline should be equated with one sidedness of training on the contrary exercises should be performed in combination which selected special exercises. These exercises should help directly or indirectly to improve the performance in the event, so that the usefulness of each individual exercise should be carefully considered.

Ability to function depends upon the physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual components of fitness, all of which are related each other and are mutually independent. This may be referred to as total fitness (Reuben B. Frost, 1971).

Methodology:

Selection of Subjects:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of bench stepping exercise on selected physiological variable such as resting pulse rate and breath holding of school-aged boys. To achieve this purpose of the study, thirty male students were selected from the Jawahar College of Arts and Sciences, Neyveli. The age of the subjects were ranged between 19 and 25 years.

Selection of Variables:

Bench step exercises are highly influenced on physical and physiological aspects. It was found from the literature that these variables might have a significant effect by the bench step exercise. Hence the research scholar earnestly got interested to know whether there was any significant improvement or not in the following variable is breath holding time.

Selection of Test:

The present study was undertaken primarily to assess the effectiveness of bench stepping exercise on selected physiological fitness variables. The investigator analysed various literatures and also consulted with physical education professional to use most suitable tests for the purpose of the study and it was presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Test Selection

S.No	Criterion Variable	Test Item	Unit of Measurement
1	Breath holding time	Holding the breath	Seconds

Collection of the Data:

The data on breath holding time were collected by administrating holding the breath for maximum duration. The data was collected at prior and immediately after the training programme separately for the criterion variable.

Statistical Technique:

The selected resting pulses rate was statistically examined by applying analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). When *F* ratio was found significant, Scheffe' S post hoc test was applied. The data was analysed with SPSS statistical package (16 version). The criterion for significance was set at an alpha level of $p < 0.05$.

Result

Breath Holding Time:

The data collected prior to and after the experimental period on breath holding time of two days per week training group, three days per week group and control group were analysed and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of covariance on breath holding time of two days per week training three days per week training and control groups

	Two Days Per Week Training Group	Three Days Per Week Training Group	Control Group	SOV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Ratio
Pre-test Mean	46.50	46.50	46.70	B:	0.267	2	0.133	0.092
S.D	1.18	1.27	1.16	W:	39.10	28	1.45	
Post-test Mean	47.90	49.10	46.50	B:	33.87	2	16.93	11.35*
S.D	0.88	0.99	1.65	W:	40.30	28	1.49	
Adjusted Post-test Mean	47.94	49.14	46.42	B:	39.11	2	18.56	19.34*
				W:	24.95	27	0.96	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence for 2 and 27 and 2 and 26 are 3.37 and 3.36).

Table 2 shows that the pre-test means of breath holding time for two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups were 46.50 ± 1.18 , 46.50 ± 1.27 and 46.70 ± 1.16 respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 0.092 for pre-test score of two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups on breath holding time was less than the required table value of 3.27 for significance with df 2 and 27 at .05 level of confidence.

The post-test mean values of breath holding time for two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups were 47.90 ± 0.88 , 49.10 ± 0.99 and 46.50 ± 1.65 respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 11.35 for post test scores of two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups was more than the required table value of 3.27 for significance with df 2 and 27 at .05 level of confidence.

The adjusted post-test mean values of two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups were 47.94, 49.14 and 46.42 respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 19.34 for adjusted post-test scores of two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups was more than the required table value of 3.28 for significance with df 3 and 26 at .05 level of confidence.

The above statistical analysis indicates that there was a significant increase in breath holding time after the training period. Further to determine which of the paired means has a significant increase, Scheffe'S test was applied. The result of the follow-up test is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Scheffe's test for the difference between the adjusted post-test mean of breath holding time

Two Days per Week Training Group	Three Days per Week Training Group	Control Group	Mean Difference	Confidence Interval at 0.05 Level
47.94	49.14		1.20	1.40
47.94		49.42	1.48*	1.40
	49.14	46.42	2.27*	1.40

*Significant at .05 level of Confidence.

Table III shows that the adjusted post-test mean difference in breath holding time between two days per week training group and three days per week training group was 1.20, which was insignificant at .05 level of confidence. The adjusted post-test mean difference between two days per week training group and control groups was 1.48, which is significant at .05 level of confidence. The adjusted post-test mean of three days per week training group and control groups was 2.72, which was significant at .05 level of confidence.

It may be concluded from the results of the study that there was a significant improvement of breath holding time after the two days and three days per week training. The mean values of two days per week training group, three days per week training group and control groups on breath holding time were graphically represented in Figure 1.

Discussion on Findings:

The results of the study also revealed that the two days per week training group and three days per week training group improved breath holding time than the control group. The result of the present study is in accordance with Thomas et al.,(1979) Robert Singer (1970), Howell et al (1966), and Laron & Johnson (1969)

Conclusions:

It was concluded that the training groups, i.e. two days per week and three days per week training, has better improvement in breath holding time.

References:

1. George, Thomas T. Annickle, "Effect of break in training on selected physiological parameters of trained athletes," Unpublished Master Thesis, Jiwaji University (1979).
2. Robert Singer and Raynld A. Weiss, Completed research, 12 (American Association 1970), pp.73-74.
3. Maxwel L. Howel, et.al "Effect of Circuit training on the Modified Harvard test", Research Quarterly 34.2,(May 1966),pp.154
4. Larson C, Effect of 5 days – a week and 2 and 3 day -a- week physical educatin class on fitness, Skill, Adipose Tissue and Growth," Research Quarterly 34.2,(March 1969),pp.93
5. Loken, Newton and Robert J. hutiously, Completed book of gymnastics, Englewood cliffs, New Jery: Prentice Hall, Inc., 1957.
6. Frost, Reuben B. Psychological Concepts applied to Physical Education and Coaching, New Delhi: Addition Wesley Publishing company, Inc., 1971.